

Cost-effectiveness analysis of interprofessional collaboration in management of blood pressure in hemodialysis outpatients with end-stage renal disease

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Abstract

This 6-month study evaluated the cost-effectiveness of an interprofessional collaboration (IPC) program for hemodialysis outpatients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD). We compared a control group ($n = 100$) with an IPC group ($n = 96$) at Dr. Pirngadi Hospital, Indonesia, from a payer's perspective. The IPC team, including a nephrologist, nurses, and pharmacists, provided integrated care. Pharmacists performed medication reconciliation, identified drug-related problems, and provided intensive education to enhance treatment adherence. Results indicated that the proportion of patients with controlled blood pressure (BP) increased from 30.00% to 73.96%. Mean BP decreased from 149.87 to 142.34 mmHg ($p < 0.001$). Total direct medical costs increased from USD 403.82 to USD 417.10 ($p < 0.001$). The cost-effectiveness ratio significantly decreased from USD 1,346.17 to USD 564.01, with an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio of USD 30.23. This study proves that IPC is a highly cost-effective intervention, as the significant clinical improvement in BP management justifies the minimal incremental cost incurred.

Keywords

Cost-effective, ESRD, hemodialysis, IPC

Introduction

End-stage renal disease (ESRD) is a major global public health issue due to the continuous increase in its morbidity and mortality. The global prevalence of ESRD was estimated to be between 4.9 and 7.1 million people (Lv and Zhang 2019), and the European Renal Association (ERA) reported 604,261 patients receiving kidney replacement

therapy for ESRD, with an overall prevalence of 931 per million population in 2020 (Astley et al. 2023). Based on data from the Indonesian Renal Registry (IRR) 2020, the number of new hemodialysis (HD) patients in Indonesia demonstrated a consistent increase from 30,831 in 2017 to 69,124 in 2019. The number of active patients reached 77,892 and 185,901 in 2019 and 2017, respectively (Perhimpunan Nefrologi Indonesia 2023). Locally, in 2019, as

many as 128 patients received hemodialysis at Dr. Pirngadi Hospital in Medan, followed by a decrease to 101 in 2020. The number of patients with hemodialysis slightly increased to 103 and 109 in 2021 and 2022, respectively.

Approximately 70.8% of patients with end-stage renal disease have one or more comorbidities, with the most common being hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease. These comorbidities significantly impact health-related quality of life, particularly in physical health domains (Cha and Han 2020; Sura et al. 2023). Patients with ESRD are particularly vulnerable to drug-related problems (DRPs) due to the complexity of their medical conditions and the extensive medication regimens they require. These problems can lead to increased morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs. A study in an HD unit at the King Hussein Medical Centre (KHMC) in Jordan identified 930 potential interactions in 277 patients (Hijazeen et al. 2020), ultimately leading to a significant increase in the overall healthcare burden. ESRD imposes a substantial economic burden on national healthcare systems, contributing between 0.91% and 7.1% of total health expenditures in selected countries (Ismail et al. 2020). The cost for a single HD session is estimated at IDR 906,000/USD 60 in Indonesia (Kementerian Kesehatan RI 2023), given that patients commonly require eight sessions monthly. Given its significant burden on mortality, morbidity, and national healthcare expenditures, end-stage renal disease demands a serious and focused management approach to improve patient outcomes and optimize resource utilization.

Hypertension is both a cause and a consequence of chronic kidney disease, and its management is crucial to reduce cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in these patients. The prevalence of hypertension in ESRD patients on hemodialysis is notably high, ranging from 72% to 88%, and is often inadequately controlled due to the complex pathophysiology involving volume overload, vascular resistance, and other factors (Symonides et al. 2024). The pathophysiology is complex, involving extracellular volume overload, increased vascular resistance, and abnormal kidney signaling (Van 2016). Accurate blood pressure monitoring is crucial, with ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) being the gold standard. Pre- and post-dialysis measurements alone are insufficient for diagnosis and management (Kim et al. 2023). We focused on blood pressure as the primary clinical outcome because it is the most critical modifiable risk factor for survival and healthcare resource utilization in ESRD. Improved BP management serves as the essential clinical evidence to justify the cost-effectiveness of the IPC program from a payer's perspective.

Various strategies have been implemented to optimize the management of patients with ESRD, including the implementation of pharmacist intervention programs (Alam et al. 2024; Khokhar et al. 2020; Paneerselvam et al. 2024). However, these discipline-specific strategies are often insufficient to meet the multifaceted needs of this complex patient population. Management of ESRD care has traditionally been physician-centric, focusing on medical

management and treatment protocols. However, previous studies have highlighted the importance of shifting towards a more patient-centered strategy by collaborating with multidisciplinary care teams. This transition aims to improve clinical outcomes, improve care coordination, and decrease direct medical costs. The integration of interprofessional teams, consisting of nurses, social workers, and dietitians, has been shown to improve patient outcomes and decrease direct medical costs compared to standard care models (Cahill and Paulus 2024; Sowa et al. 2020). Additionally, a Comprehensive ESRD Care (CEC) model has shown significant results in reducing hospitalizations and readmissions, emphasizing the need for specialty-oriented care models that focus on patient outcomes rather than standard care (Ullman et al. 2022). The multidisciplinary approach remains a promising strategy for improving patient outcomes and quality of life in ESRD patients. Future strategies must focus on standardizing the IPC program and evaluating it for long-term impacts (Marcos et al. 2024). Previous studies suggest that adopting an IPC model is not just an improvement but a fundamental necessity for providing high-quality, comprehensive, and cost-effective care to patients with ESRD.

In Indonesia and many other countries, the management of ESRD and hemodialysis care remains predominantly focused on the nephrologist. This physician-centric approach often limits comprehensive care, despite evidence suggesting that collaborative efforts among medical professionals can significantly improve patient outcomes. The cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) of an IPC model for hemodialysis patients remains exceptionally limited, particularly in the context of Indonesia. Evaluating the effectiveness of IPC through a CEA is a crucial strategy to ensure a positive impact on patient outcomes and the sustainable management of resources in ESRD care.

Methods

Study design

This 6-month retrospective–prospective quasi-experimental study analyzed the cost-effectiveness of IPC in hemodialysis outpatients with ESRD admitted to Dr. Pirngadi Hospital, Medan, Indonesia, in 2024. The pharmacoeconomic evaluation was conducted from the perspective of the national health insurance, called Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Kesehatan (BPJS); thus, only direct medical costs were measured in this study. The costs incurred by both groups included drug acquisition, chronic medications, consumable medical supplies, laboratory tests, and professional fees. To determine the effectiveness of IPC, the primary clinical outcome measured was the proportion of patients who achieved controlled blood pressure in both groups. This analytical framework allowed for the calculation of key metrics, including the cost-effectiveness ratio (CER) and incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), to determine the value of the IPC intervention.

Study population and sampling

The study population comprised all ESRD patients receiving treatment at Dr. Pirngadi Hospital in Medan, Indonesia, between April and September 2024. A consecutive sampling technique was employed to ensure that all patients who met the predefined eligibility criteria during the study period were included. The minimum required sample size was determined to be 85 patients, calculated using OpenEpi software with a 95% confidence interval. To be eligible for inclusion, patients must have been undergoing regular outpatient hemodialysis for at least 3 months, were enrolled in the national health insurance program, and provided written informed consent. Comorbidities were documented but did not serve as a basis for exclusion. Conversely, the study excluded patients diagnosed with cancer currently undergoing chemotherapy and those with documented mental disorders to ensure the reliability of the clinical and adherence data.

Interprofessional collaboration team

The IPC intervention was implemented through a structured and coordinated workflow involving physicians, pharmacists, and nurses, designed to transition from a traditional physician-centric model to a more holistic, integrated care approach. Within this team, the physicians—comprising a consultant nephrologist and a certified internal medicine specialist—were responsible for overall clinical management, establishing blood pressure targets, and making final decisions regarding medication adjustments. Pharmacists, with at least 2 years of clinical pharmacy experience, played a crucial role as medication therapy experts by performing systematic medication reconciliation, identifying drug-related problems, and evaluating the appropriateness of dosage regimens. Furthermore, pharmacists provided intensive bedside counseling focused on medication adherence and side-effect management, which served as a primary driver for successful BP control. Dialysis-certified nurses supported this process through real-time hemodynamic monitoring during sessions and by reinforcing the lifestyle modifications and treatment instructions initiated by both physicians and pharmacists.

This collaborative process followed a continuous cycle of review, consultation, and education. The workflow commenced with a comprehensive medication review by the pharmacist to identify any drug interactions or inconsistencies that could hinder BP management. Subsequently, the team held brief huddles to discuss patients with uncontrolled BP, where the pharmacist provided evidence-based recommendations for drug optimization that were then reviewed and approved by the physician. Unlike standard care, the IPC group received harmonized and integrated patient education; while nurses focused on fluid restriction and dietary requirements, pharmacists delivered structured counseling on antihypertensive adherence using visual aids. This coordinated effort among qualified professionals was conducted routinely during every dialysis cycle to ensure consistent monitoring of patient progress, forming the fundamental basis for the successful IPC intervention in this study.

Data collection and intervention

The IPC intervention began with medication reconciliation, where the clinical pharmacist, in a coordinated effort with the physicians and nurses, systematically reviewed the patients' medications to identify and resolve any medication problems. Following the patient visit, the entire team conducted a discussion to review and finalize the patient's treatment plan in detail, ensuring a coordinated and consistent decision. This collaborative review specifically targeted antihypertensive optimization, as blood pressure was identified as the primary surrogate marker for cardiovascular stability and long-term survival in this ESRD cohort. The IPC team then provided medication therapy management by continuously monitoring the patients' responses to their treatments and making collective adjustments to the drug regimen. BP was rigorously monitored during each session to evaluate the immediate clinical impact of these pharmacological adjustments. Consistent and coordinated patient education was provided, with each team member reinforcing the importance of appropriate use of medications and treatment adherence. By focusing on BP control, the team aimed to minimize the risk of fluid overload and hypertensive crises, which are the leading drivers of hospitalization in dialysis patients. This holistic and shared approach to care was designed to proactively manage the patients' condition and significantly improve outcomes.

Economic and statistical analysis

Cost-effectiveness analysis was conducted to compare the costs and outcomes in the IPC intervention group against the group with standard care. The cost-effectiveness ratio (CER) was calculated for each group, while the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) was the key metric used to evaluate the additional cost incurred by the IPC group to achieve one additional unit of outcome compared to the standard care group. A one-way sensitivity analysis was performed to test the robustness of the study's findings by varying key variables. All statistical computations and data analysis were conducted using SPSS program version 30.00. The conversion of all cost data from Indonesian Rupiah (IDR) to US dollars (USD) was performed to facilitate international comparison. We applied the 2024 average exchange rate of 1 USD = 16,690.90 IDR for all calculations.

Results

Clinical characteristic of hemodialysis patients with ESRD

The mean age of the patients was 50.01 ± 11.24 years. Most (67%) patients were male and suffered from hypertension, congestive heart failure, diabetes, anemia, and hyperphosphatemia. Most (74%) of these patients have received hemodialysis for 1 to 5 years.

Effectiveness of the IPC

The effectiveness of the IPC intervention in reducing the blood pressure of the patients before and after IPC is shown in Table 1. Blood pressure was considered controlled if it was at or below the target threshold of 140/90 mmHg.

The data presented in Table 1 demonstrates a significant improvement in the proportion of patients with blood pressure control following the IPC intervention. Prior to the program, the mean blood pressure was 149.87 ± 17.07 mmHg, with a majority (70%) of the patients having uncontrolled blood pressure. After the IPC program, the mean blood pressure decreased to 142.34 ± 9.61 mmHg, resulting in a notable additional 43.96% increase in the patients with controlled blood pressure. This improvement in blood pressure status was statistically significant, as confirmed by the Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Blood pressure in patients before and after IPC.

Blood Pressure	n	(%)	Mean BP (mmHg)	% increase in patients with controlled BP after IPC	Wilcoxon (Asymp. sig)
Before IPC					
Controlled	30	30.00	$149.87 \pm$	43.96	< 0.001
Uncontrolled	70	70.00	17.07		
After IPC					
Controlled	69	73.96	$142.34 \pm$		
Uncontrolled	25	26.04	9.61		

Direct medical cost

Table 2 provides a detailed comparison of the direct medical costs per patient per month before and after the IPC program.

The data presented in Table 2 reveals a statistically significant increase in total direct medical costs following the IPC intervention, rising from USD 403.85 to USD 417.14 ($p < 0.001$). A breakdown of the cost components shows that three components of the resources consumed, including chronic medications, laboratory tests, and professional fees, increased significantly in the group with IPC ($p < 0.001$). Costs for consumable medical supplies (syringes, infuse sets, planters, alcohol swabs, gauze, gloves, and masks) and consumable sets (dialysates, blood lines, AV fistulas, and dialyzers) remained the same in both groups.

Cost-effective analysis

Results of the cost-effectiveness analysis in groups before and after IPC are presented in Table 3. This table presents the findings of the cost-effectiveness analysis, providing a direct comparison of patient outcomes and associated costs before and after the IPC intervention. The analysis includes the calculation of the CER and the ICER to evaluate the program's efficiency.

The results of the cost-effectiveness analysis demonstrate that the IPC program is highly cost-effective in

Table 2. Direct medical costs per patient per month before and after IPC (USD).

Direct Costs (IDR)	Before IPC (n = 100)	After IPC (n = 96)	p-value
Chronic medications	2.57	3.40	< 0.001
Drug acquisition costs	64.89	64.28	0.852
Consumable medical supplies	6.15	6.15	1.000
Consumable set	277.37	277.37	1.000
Laboratory tests	10.90	17.97	< 0.001
Professional fees	41.94	47.93	< 0.001
Total costs	403.85	417.14	< 0.001

Table 3. Cost-effectiveness analysis before and after IPC.

Variables	Before IPC (n = 100)	After IPC (n = 96)
% patients with controlled BP	30.00	73.96
Direct cost/100 patients	USD 40,385.01	USD 41,714.03
CER	USD 1,346.17	USD 564.01
ICER		USD 30.23

improving the blood pressure of these patients. Before the intervention, the CER, or the costs consumed to achieve blood pressure control for one patient, was USD 1,346.17. Following the IPC program, the CER significantly decreased to USD 564.01. The ICER calculated was USD 30.23, which represents the additional cost required to achieve one additional percentage point of patients with controlled blood pressure. This low ICER value suggests that the IPC program was a cost-effective strategy for improving the management of patients with ESRD.

The pharmacoeconomic quadrant plot is shown in Fig. 1. This plot is a standard method used to visually depict the trade-off between the costs and effectiveness of IPC compared to before IPC (standard treatment). This present study indicated that the position of the IPC program relative to standard care (SC) was in quadrant 2. Based on the WHO threshold, IPC is still considered a cost-effective program, since the ICER is much lower than three times the income per capita for 2024 (income per capita for 2024 was IDR 78,600,000/USD 4,710.65) (Badan Pusat Statistik 2025).

The quadrant plot demonstrates the position of the IPC intervention in relation to standard care (SC), which is set at the origin. The IPC program is located in Quadrant II, indicating that it is more expensive but also more effective than standard care. The coordinates of the IPC point show an incremental direct medical cost of IDR 22,180,714.50 (USD 1,329.22) on the x-axis and an incremental effectiveness of 43.96% on the y-axis, representing the percentage increase in patients with controlled blood pressure. This position confirms that the IPC program is not a dominated strategy (i.e., not more expensive and less effective) but rather a viable alternative that offers superior clinical outcomes at a higher cost. The decision to adopt the program would therefore depend on the healthcare system's willingness-to-pay threshold for achieving a significant increase in blood pressure control.

Figure 1. Pharmacoeconomic quadrant plot comparing IPC to standard care.

Results of sensitivity analysis

The Tornado Diagram illustrates the results of the one-way sensitivity analysis conducted to assess the robustness of the base-case ICER, defined as the additional cost (IDR) per patient achieving controlled BP. This analysis systematically varied the key cost parameters by 20% (both increase and decrease) to determine their relative influence on the ICER.

The diagram clearly indicates that the ICER is most sensitive to variations in the cost of the consumable set, with a 20% change causing the largest fluctuation of IDR 2,106,274.80/USD 126.88 in the ICER value. Following this, drug acquisition costs (up to IDR 488,118.31/USD 29.40) and professional fees (up to IDR 363,967.2/USD 21.93) demonstrated a noticeable impact. Conversely, the ICER proved to be least sensitive to uncertainty in the cost of chronic medication (up to IDR 25,834.09/USD 1.56), suggesting that the cost-effectiveness conclusion is primarily driven by the cost assumptions related to consumables.

Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the clinical and economic outcomes of an IPC program for hemodialysis patients with ESRD. The findings provide a robust basis for discussing the implementation of such collaborative models within the Indonesian healthcare context. The demographic data of the study sample, with a majority of male patients and a mean age of approximately 50 years, aligns with global epidemiological trends of ESRD. End-stage renal disease disproportionately impacts older adults, with age being a key factor in its prevalence and outcomes. Previous studies indicated that the majority of ESRD patients were in the age range of 40–70 years (Abdulla et al.

2017; Almutairi et al. 2017; Shella and Nunuk 2022; Choudhary et al. 2024). This demographic trend highlights the increasing incidence of ESRD among the elderly population.

The clinical results of our study demonstrate a significant improvement in the proportion of patients with target blood pressure following the IPC intervention. The proportion of patients with controlled blood pressure increased from 30.00% to 73.96% ($p < 0.001$), a finding that strongly supports the effectiveness of an interprofessional approach. This result is consistent with a prior study that has shown how the integration of multidisciplinary teams, including nurses, pharmacists, and dietitians, leads to improved patient outcomes and better care coordination compared to standard care, physician-centric models (Cahill and Paulus 2024; Murray et al. 2013). These findings underscore that IPC does not merely improve numerical BP values but fundamentally stabilizes the patient's clinical state, which is the most critical modifiable factor in preventing cardiovascular complications. Consequently, the achievement of such high control rates (73.96%) provides the essential clinical justification for the intervention's cost-effectiveness, as it directly reduces the long-term risk of high-cost emergency interventions.

Previous studies have indicated that multidisciplinary care is often a cost-effective alternative to standard care models. The integration of various professionals has been shown to improve patient outcomes and reduce healthcare costs (Chen et al. 2014; Lin et al. 2018; Moraes et al. 2021). This present study indicated a statistically significant increase in the total direct medical costs after the IPC intervention, a finding primarily driven by a significant increase in chronic medication costs ($p < 0.001$). While a slight increase in professional fees was an expected consequence of the IPC program's implementation, this particular change was not statistically significant. This outcome suggests that the higher costs consumed were largely attributable

Figure 2. Tornado diagram of IPC for hemodialysis patients with ESRD.

to more intensive and optimized medication regimens, which are necessary to achieve better clinical outcomes. This finding positions the IPC program as more effective but also more expensive than standard care, a conclusion visually supported by its placement in Quadrant II of the pharmacoeconomic plot. The calculated ICER of IDR 504,565.84 (USD 30.23) represents the additional cost required to achieve one additional percentage point of patients with controlled blood pressure. This ICER value is a critical metric for healthcare policymakers, who must consider this cost against their willingness-to-pay threshold. The favorable CER and ICER findings indicate that the IPC program, despite its higher cost, provides substantial clinical value, making it an efficient and economically justifiable strategy for improving patient outcomes.

Ultimately, this study's findings provide strong evidence that moving away from traditional, single-specialty care to an interprofessional collaborative model is not merely a beneficial option but a fundamental necessity for providing high-quality, comprehensive, and cost-effective care to patients with ESRD. The IPC program offers a promising solution to the significant morbidity and mortality burden of ESRD by demonstrating that an initial investment in a coordinated team approach yields substantial and statistically significant improvements in a critical clinical outcome such as blood pressure control. This study demonstrates that interprofessional collaboration (IPC) provides a dual benefit by significantly improving clinical outcomes alongside documented cost-effectiveness, a combination rarely evidenced in developing health systems. Our findings confirm the feasibility of integrating clinical pharmacists into the core dialysis team within the national health insurance framework, offering a scalable model for resource-limited settings. Given that IPC remains underutilized in such contexts, this research provides a robust clinical basis for its adoption, showing that coordinated care directly enhances blood pressure control while maintaining sustainable healthcare expenditures.

Study limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Firstly, the short duration of the study limits our ability to assess the long-term sustainability of the observed improvements and the potential for a delayed impact on controlled blood pressure and costs. Secondly, the variety of complications among the patients, such as anemia and hyperphosphatemia, creates a high degree of clinical heterogeneity, which is a potential source of bias in measuring the intervention's effectiveness. Therefore, future studies with a larger sample size, a randomized controlled trial design, and a longer follow-up period are needed to further validate these findings.

Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence that the IPC program is a highly effective and economically viable strategy for improving blood pressure control among hemodialysis patients with ESRD. These findings should be considered by health policymakers to ensure high-quality care in the management of ESRD patients.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Ethical approval for this study was granted by an Ethics Committee in Indonesia (No. 436/KEPK/USU/2024).

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

PP: Concept, project administration, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, writing original draft. AN: Concept, project administration, supervision, formal analysis, writing original draft. AAS: Supervision, formal analysis, writing review editing. ATN: Supervision, formal analysis, writing review editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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